

TECHNIQUES FOR EVALUATING THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF
AVIONICS SUBSYSTEMS TO FIGHTER AIRCRAFT OPERATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

by

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Summary

Experiences on the Integrated Control and Avionics for Air Superiority (ICAAS) program are used to discuss various methods for validating avionics system performance in the air-to-air mission. Digital air battle simulation, using the TAC BRAWLER and AASPEM computer programs, proved to be an effective screening tool for identifying first-order mission effectiveness trends during concept definition and preliminary design studies. Part task simulations added the human element to the evaluation and were used to define and evaluate the pilot/vehicle interface. Full-mission manned simulations provide the most comprehensive and accurate assessment of the performance of the integrated avionics system in the air-to-air mission. Piloted mission simulations benefit from a well-defined baseline, simulator verification tests, and from the participation of an independent White Force team. Finally, the flight test program is described and justified as a limited but necessary real world validation and demonstration of system performance benefits.

Introduction

The Integrated Control and Avionics for Air Superiority (ICAAS) program is an Air Force funded effort whose objective is to develop, integrate, and demonstrate technologies to enable USAF fighter aircraft to kill and survive when outnumbered by enemy aircraft during air combat engagements. Primary emphasis is placed on beyond-visual-range (BVR) multiple target attack capability with provisions for effective transition to close-in combat. Sensor information is processed and recommended actions are displayed to aid the pilot in selecting and executing the most effective attack and defend engagement options. The ICAAS system will attempt to maximize opportunities for missile launch against multiple enemy aircraft while maintaining options to defend when necessary. Sufficient integration and automation are provided for application to a single seat fighter aircraft.¹

To achieve ICAAS program objectives, several advanced avionics subsystems and functional capabilities are incorporated on current and future fighter aircraft configurations and evaluated by means of analysis, manned simulations, and/or flight testing. Avionics subsystems to be investigated include an intraflight data link, advanced targeting sensors (electro-optic and radar), large multi-purpose color cockpit displays,

active and passive missile warning sensors, and advanced on-board and off-board electronic countermeasures. The computational capabilities that integrate these avionics subsystems provide the pilot-aiding functions which form the basis of the ICAAS program. These pilot-aiding functions to be evaluated include: 1) an attack management system for sensor control, track file management, fire control, and internetting; 2) a knowledge-based tactics algorithm that assesses the combat situation and makes tactical recommendations to the pilot; 3) a flight management system for optimizing offensive and defensive trajectories; and 4) a missile evasion function which coordinates maneuvers and countermeasures to defeat incoming air-to-air missiles. The program employs a systematic build-up approach to the development and mission effectiveness evaluation of the avionics technologies and functions that comprise the ICAAS system.

Digital Simulations

The initial phase of the ICAAS program involved two separate contractors performing concept definition and preliminary design studies. General Dynamics and the McDonnell Aircraft Company were the two contractors chosen for this one-year effort. Their early work focused on selecting appropriate air-to-air missions, defining required operational capabilities, screening candidate avionics technologies for integration, and developing a program road map to achieve the required levels of mission performance. Digital simulation proved to be an effective technique for screening candidate air-to-air avionics technologies to determine those that offered the highest operational payoff potential.

General Dynamics chose the TAC BRAWLER digital analysis simulation tool for conducting trade studies to evaluate the contributions of avionics technologies to the air superiority mission.² TAC BRAWLER was developed by Decision Science Applications under Air Force sponsorship and has achieved widespread acceptance for high-fidelity air-to-air engagement modeling involving large numbers of players. It operates on Monte Carlo principles and provides physical models (aircraft, weapons, avionics), human factors models, and production rules.

The basic 2 versus 8 scenario used by General

Dynamics in their TAC BRAWLER digital simulations is shown in Figure 1. With this basic scenario held constant, avionics technologies and functions were varied individually and in combination to evaluate their contributions to overall mission effectiveness as measured by Loss Exchange Ratio (LER). (LER is defined as the number of enemy losses divided by the number of friendly losses.) This technique was also used to define the "knee of the curve" beyond which further increases in an avionics capability results in no significant increase in operational payoff. Figure 2 is an example of the results of such a sensitivity study on sensor detection ranges. In this case, it was found that a sensor suite capable of detecting the enemy at 170 nautical miles would maximize the LER, all other parameters being held constant. The results of such sensitivity studies were used to set ICAAS program design goals only in cases where the optimal value was also achievable within the technology state-of-the-art during the time period of ICAAS program interest (the years 1995 to 2002). For this example, and considering the advent of Low Observables (LO) technology, it was judged unrealistic to expect target detections from an on-board sensor suite at ranges anywhere near the 170 nautical mile optimum. Therefore, further studies used lower target detection ranges that resulted from projected near term radar performance capabilities. Nonetheless, this sensitivity study showed the magnitude of mission effectiveness improvement that could be expected by improving sensor performance and that this parameter is an important player in air-to-air combat success.

Figure 1: Scenario Starting Conditions

The final series of TAC BRAWLER runs compared the mission effectiveness of an aircraft equipped with candidate ICAAS avionics technologies and functions with a baseline aircraft not so equipped. The results are presented in Figure 3 and were used to indicate the technology areas offering the highest payoff potential. While Figure 3 shows incremental improvements from the individual technologies, similar charts were plotted showing

the cumulative effects of combining capabilities to get a feel for synergism effects. As shown in Figure 3, a missile evasion algorithm, an intraflight data link for situation awareness, and long range weapons were the big payoff technologies.

Figure 2: Effect of Sensor Detection Range

Figure 3: TAC BRAWLER Results

An analysis tool as complicated and powerful as TAC BRAWLER obviously has great potential for misuse, especially if the analyst knows the "right" answer going in and will be presenting his results to an audience lacking expertise in the technique. TAC BRAWLER does not have on/off switches for such functions as data links and missile evasion algorithms. Such functions must be approximated by modifying physical models or by using production rules that will result in the desired effect. For instance, missile evasion capability was evaluated by lowering threat missile probabilities of kill based on survivability results from previous contracted efforts. As another example, the data link was emulated by programming complete and perfect verbal communications between friendly

fighters. It is important that the sponsor of such digital simulations either specify the rules, models and scenarios to be used or be fully knowledgeable of them. General Dynamics effectively diffused any possible "garbage in/garbage out" accusations by keeping the Air Force fully informed of all assumptions, limitations, production rules, and physical models used in their TAC BRAWLER analysis. They also presented a two-day tutorial on TAC BRAWLER and their use of it on the ICAAS program, and made a good case for its use as an initial top-level sorting and screening tool for avionics technologies.

McDonnell Aircraft elected to use the AASPEM (Advanced Air-to-air System Performance Evaluation Model) digital simulation tool in their preliminary ICAAS design efforts.³ The scope of McDonnell Aircraft's AASPEM analysis effort during the first year of the ICAAS contract was comparable to that of General Dynamic's TAC BRAWLER work. After McDonnell Aircraft was awarded contract options to continue the ICAAS development beyond the first year, they focused their AASPEM simulations on quantifying operational benefits from tactics that would be enabled by advanced avionics capabilities. Two such tactics are called "cooperative launch" and "detached mutual support" and both are designed to exploit the intra-flight data link.

The cooperative launch concept is depicted in Figure 4. The lead friendly aircraft operates passively and receives target information, via the data link, from the trailing aircraft. After the lead aircraft has launched its missiles, it breaks away from the engagement and the tracking aircraft continues target tracking and missile guidance. This tactic effectively increases the "F-pole" of the missile. (F-pole is defined as the distance between the shooter and target at time of missile impact.)

The results of AASPEM analysis of the cooperative launch tactic for a 2 versus 8 head-on air-to-air engagement are shown in Figure 5. This figure indicates a 4 to 1 improvement in loss exchange ratio (LER) from cooperative launch under conditions where the threat aircraft can detect the friendly fighter at ranges greater than 20 nautical miles. Figure 5 also shows that friendly fighter Low Observable (LO) technology itself produces a big LER benefit and negates the need for the cooperative launch tactic.

Detached mutual support refers to the capability of a flight of aircraft to operate effectively as a team despite being out of sight of each other. Providing support to a wingman, whether close-in or detached, has two prerequisites: 1) knowing what's happening to your wingman and 2) being able to do something about it. For detached mutual support, the situation awareness requirement is satisfied by sharing and displaying track file information using a data link. The second requirement is addressed by beyond-visual-range (BVR) weapons. The ICAAS concept incorporates both a data link and BVR missiles. Therefore, detached mutual support is a natural area for investigation under the program.

Figure 4: Cooperative Launch Concept

McDonnell Aircraft used the AASPEM program to explore the operational benefits to be gained from detached mutual support. They conducted parametric studies using a variety of threat aircraft in AWACS defense, base defense, and bomber escort missions. The parameters varied included initial altitudes, airspeeds, separation distances, and headings. Friendly aircraft lateral and lead-trail separation distances investigated were 2, 10, 20, and 30 nautical miles. Numerical results are classified, but the AASPEM simulations indicate that significant exchange ratio improvements can be gained by operating at separation distances well outside of visual contact ranges.

Figure 5: Cooperative Launch AASPEM Results

Both the TAC BRAWLER and AASPEN digital analysis tools were effectively applied during the concept definition and preliminary design stages of the ICAAS program. These simulation techniques are best at identifying first order effects of major avionics systems that are straightforward to model. Since the results depend heavily on the rules, scenarios, and modeling assumptions, it is important that these be well understood and documented and that the analyst be experienced with the tool and have a high degree of integrity. Limitations will usually be encountered using digital simulations to analyze new capabilities or tactics, especially those that require human interaction. For instance, an eight-color 9 1/2 inch multi-purpose display is a part of the ICAAS improved pilot/vehicle interface that did not lend itself to a mission-level effects analysis. Assumptions could have been made that this display would have resulted in XX fewer situation awareness mistakes by the pilot, and this effect could have been propagated through the digital simulation to get a loss exchange increment. Unless backed up by hard data, this type of assumption should be avoided to maintain credibility in digital simulation results. The ICAAS program chose to postpone such evaluations until a pilot could become directly involved.

Part Task Simulations

In the ICAAS program, part task simulations bridged the gap between digital analyses and the full-up manned mission simulation evaluation of the integrated avionics system. This technique offered two advantages over the digital air battle analysis approach. First, it introduced the advantage of human interaction and allowed pilot exposure to the system in the preliminary design stages. Second, the actual algorithms, as opposed to effects models, could be implemented and updated as the design progressed from concept to actual flightworthy hardware and software. The application of part task simulation techniques helped identify problems sooner and greatly reduced the need for later, more expensive modifications to configuration-controlled software.

Part task simulations were conducted in several different environments, depending on the purpose and degree of fidelity required for a given experiment. The simplest of these environments was a static cockpit mockup with cardboard panels holding proposed display formats. On a much higher level of complexity, a Rapid Prototyping Workstation provided two independently controlled friendly aircraft flying against as many as eight reactive digital threat aircraft. This provided pilots and operations analysts a better insight into the payoffs from avionics systems than could be gained from digital air battle simulations. A part task simulation capability that gave development engineers insight into the workings of the evolving design was the Software Test Facility (STF). The STF was used to integrate ICAAS hardware and software components. It also provided reactive targets and as much flight hardware as possible to validate the design and resolve interface problems prior to full-up hardware in the

loop manned simulations. Finally, a 40-foot dome mission simulator served as a part task simulation tool for evaluating such factors as display color coding and format switchology.

It became apparent early in the program that a dedicated cadre of pilots was needed to support the development of the ICAAS avionics system. A Pilot Evaluation Group (PEG) was formed which consisted of six members divided between Air Force and contractor pilots. The PEG met about every three months during ICAAS system development. These meetings were usually held in conjunction with a part task simulation event. The PEG was invaluable in developing the pilot/vehicle interface (PVI) to fully exploit the complex ICAAS avionics system.

The baseline cockpit display suite for the ICAAS program is shown in Figure 6. The arrangement of the three multi-purpose displays (MPD) was chosen to maximize the available display area within the confines of an existing F-15 cockpit. The left and right MPDs are each 6 inches on a side and are normally used as an air-to-air sensor display and a tactics display, respectively. The large center display is the primary situation awareness display and measures 9 1/2 inches on a side. The display suite also includes a low profile head-up display (HUD) and a helmet mounted display (HMD). Part task simulation was the primary technique for defining the display configurations and the physical interaction between the pilot and the avionics system.

Figure 6: Cockpit Displays

The part task simulations did not have to start from scratch in defining the basic symbology to use on the multi-purpose displays. Previous contractor work, the Joint Tactical Information Distribution System (JTIDS) program, and the Air-to-Air Attack Management (A³M) program all contributed to the display symbology.⁴ The part task simulations concentrated on ICAAS-unique display requirements. These included such

considerations as how to display recommended 4-dimensional tactics paths (position and time) on a 2-dimensional screen, how to cue the pilot for a missile evasion maneuver, how to show threat missile launch envelopes, how to depict figures of merit, how to exploit color coding to the fullest extent, and how to show recommended missile launch points. The typical course of action was to have a contractor pilot/engineer propose a candidate display which would be coded and shown to the full PEG in a part task simulation environment. The PEG would then collectively decide on the adequacy of the proposed display and suggest alternatives as appropriate. This process proved very effective and gave confidence that reasonable symbology would be taken forward into the formal mission simulations. It was found that engineers were tempted to display more information than the pilots could readily assimilate under combat conditions. Therefore, as the design matured the symbology became less complex with more levels of declutter being provided to the pilot. The tactics multi-purpose display format that resulted from PEG participation in part task simulations is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Tactics Display Symbology

The switchology associated with the display suite was also largely designed using part task simulation. Three methods are available to the pilot for controlling the large center situation awareness multi-purpose display: 1) hands-on throttle and stick (HOTAS) switches, 2) the bezel switches located around the perimeter of the display, and 3) a touch sensitive overlay. Some Pilot Evaluation Group members believe that flight testing will show that the touch sensitive overlay is not a practical input method in a flight environment. The two side displays provide HOTAS and bezel switches for pilot control.

Tactics selection by the pilot is accomplished using the row of switches along the top of the Figure 7 display. These switches provide the pilot with up to five candidate tactical recommendations arranged from left to right in descending order of desirability. The "4444, 333, 22" is designed to indicate at a glance the desirability rating of each tactic that could be previewed by selecting the corresponding switch. This example illustrates the difficulty of designing and evaluating the pilot/vehicle interface (PVI) for a system as complex as ICAAS. The initial design used a string of "X"s to indicate desirability rating. No decision has been made on whether the current design is the best way to give the pilot access to tactical options and whether five options are excessive in the heat of battle. Some PEG members believe that the pilot should be able to specify his "favorite" tactic in advance so that it always appears as one of the options. Part task simulations are continuing to address these and other issues related to the ICAAS PVI.

Part task simulations also played an important role in development of the ICAAS tactics algorithm. The first step in this process was to conduct literature searches and interviews with operational TAC pilots to determine current day, conventional tactics and also to get a feel for tactical possibilities that would be enabled by advanced avionics technologies. From this process came a "knowledge-based" geometry tree algorithm that selects tactics based on scenario, threat information, own aircraft status, and pilot preference weighting factors that are entered in advance. A part task simulation environment was then used to show TAC pilots a series of scenarios and the tactical recommendations that the tactics algorithm generated. The question posed to the pilots was, "Given this scenario, is the tactical recommendation reasonable?" In this manner, the tactics algorithm was evaluated and refined as appropriate.

The "big picture" result of ICAAS part task simulations was a realization that PVI is a major system integration issue. Even though the ICAAS system automates tasks that traditionally have fallen to the pilot (sensor mode control, sensor search volumes), there is still a great potential to overload the pilot with information and options. In a system as complex and powerful as ICAAS, effective cockpit data management techniques are required, including a proper balance between automation and manual task allocation. It is essential to achieve a user-friendly implementation of an integrated avionics system to achieve pilot acceptance. Even with the best PVI attainable, extensive training will be needed to achieve the pilot proficiency levels necessary to fully exploit the capability afforded by the ICAAS system.

Full-Mission Manned Simulations

High fidelity piloted simulation is expected to be the evaluation technique that provides the most comprehensive and accurate assessment of the

performance of the ICAAS integrated avionics system in the air-to-air mission. The manned mission simulations will begin with 2 friendly versus 4 enemy aircraft force mixes and will build up to 4 friendly versus 16 enemy aircraft. Friendly forces will have fully configured cockpits and outside visual scenes including threat and friendly aircraft, sky/earth references, and missiles. At least half of the enemy forces will consist of manned combat stations, augmented with digital aircraft models to achieve the full complement of threat aircraft. Air Force tactical fighter pilots will serve as test subjects, with separate friendly and threat teams. The threat aircraft consist of current and projected Soviet fighters and air-to-air missiles and will be employed using assumed Soviet tactical doctrine. Three different air-to-air mission scenarios are being examined: 1) bomber escort, 2) air base defense, and 3) AWACS defense against high, fast flyers.

The top-level simulation test matrix is presented in Figure 8. A necessity in any attempt to quantify performance improvements is to have a well-defined baseline for comparison. The ICAAS test matrix has two such baselines. Block 1 is the F-15 baseline with a Mechanically Scanned Antenna (MSA) radar, no intraflight data link, a standard F-15C cockpit, no Low Observability (LO) features, and no ICAAS flight management or attack management capability. The second baseline is defined in Block 8. This baseline is representative of the next generation high performance front-line USAF fighter having an Electronically Scanned Antenna (ESA) radar, an intraflight data link, three glass cockpit displays, LO signatures, and an attack management system based on the Air-to-Air Attack Management program. Missing from this fighter are the ICAAS flight management functions, whose performance increments will be obtained by comparing Block 9 results with the Block 8 baseline. The performance increments resulting from applying full-up ICAAS functions to a current

day fighter will fall out of the comparison of Block 3 to Block 1 results. It can be seen by examining the Figure 8 test matrix that other blocks were designed to also quantify the individual performance increments resulting from an ESA radar, an attack management system, LO technologies, and an intraflight data link. Other blocks will investigate the effects of weather (Block 12) and of the Electronic Warfare (EW) environment (Blocks 6 and 13) on ICAAS system performance. Block 7 will produce manned simulation results that can be compared directly to data obtained from flight tests.

Three separate and major manned simulation sessions are planned at the contractor facilities under the ICAAS program. Each will use the basic test matrix, but system capabilities will be varied to correspond to performance levels typical of the years 1995, 1998, and 2002. By way of examples, the first simulation entry features an ESA radar with a field of regard of $\pm 70^\circ$ in azimuth. This is increased to $\pm 120^\circ$ in the last entry to correspond to the expected availability of "cheek array" technology. Countermeasure technology progresses from current day chaff and flares to conceptual RF towed decoys in the last simulation entry. Self protection system ranges and angular coverages increase between simulation entries. Data link ranges and sophistication of the tactics algorithm also progress. AMRAAM improvements are postulated which would increase its range and radar sensitivity in the last simulation entry. Corresponding performance improvements are also granted to enemy capabilities. For instance, while the AA-10C is the threat medium range missile in the first simulation, the projected Soviet FOMRAAM (Follow On Medium Range Air-to-Air Missile) becomes the primary threat missile for the last of the three mission simulations.

The Air Force project office considers the output of the three piloted mission simulations to

Blk	Friendly/Threat Detectability	Aero & Perf	PVI	Sensors/Att Mgmt	Data Link	Flt Mgmt	Comments
1	F-15/F-15	F-15	F-15	MSA	Off	Non-ICAAS	Baseline F-15
2	F-15/F-15	F-15	ADV	ESA + IAM	On	Non-ICAAS	Effect of IAM on F-15
3	F-15/F-15	F-15	ADV	ESA + IAM	On	ICAAS	Full-up ICAAS F-15
4	F-15/F-15	F-15	ADV	MSA + IAM	On	ICAAS	Effect of ESA
5	F-15/F-15	ADV	ADV	ESA + IAM	On	ICAAS	Effect of Aero/Perf & ESA
6	LO/Vary	ADV	ADV	ESA + IAM	On	ICAAS	Effect of EW level 1
7	F-15/EAFB A/C	F-15	ADV	MSA + IAM	Off	ICAAS	1 vs n Flight Test Config
8	LO/F-15	ADV	ADV	ESA + IAM	On	Non-ICAAS	Effect of big LO Advantage
9	LO/Vary	ADV	ADV	ESA + IAM	On	ICAAS	Nominal Sim Configuration
10	LO/Vary	ADV	ADV	ESA + IAM	Off	ICAAS	Delta due to Data Link
11	LO/Vary	ADV	ADV	ESA + IAM	On	Non-ICAAS	Effect of Flight Mgmt
12	LO/Vary	ADV	ADV	ESA + IAM	On	ICAAS	Effect of Weather
13	LO/Vary	ADV	ADV	ESA + IAM	On	ICAAS	Effect of EW level 2

LO: Low Observable
 EAFB: Edwards AFB
 A/C: Aircraft
 ADV: Advanced
 MSA: Mechanically Scanned Antenna Radar
 ESA: Electronically Scanned Antenna Radar
 IAM: ICAAS Attack Management Function
 EW: Electronic Warfare

Figure 8: Mission Simulation Test Matrix

be the primary technical product of the ICAAS program. Therefore, much attention has been directed to assuring the validity of the simulation setup, its conduct, the data collection process, and the analysis of results. The Air Force has defined and conducted independent engineering tests on the contractor's simulator to validate aircraft, missile, and avionics system models. It is also sponsoring major in-house ICAAS piloted mission simulations which will spot check contractor results and extend the areas of investigation. The Air Force has also contracted with Veda Inc to exploit that firm's experience with similar mission simulations, most notably the AMRAAM Operational Utility Evaluation. Veda has performed constructive reviews of the contractor's simulation planning documents and has written a plan for their independent analysis of the McDonnell Aircraft simulation data. In the process, they have suggested an expanded list of Measures of Performance/Measures of Effectiveness (MOPs/MOEs). One good idea was to augment the standard Loss Exchange Ratio (LER) MOE with a measure that considers overall mission success. For defense missions, the MOE takes into account the number of enemy bombers reaching the defended asset in addition to friendly and threat aircraft losses. Finally, the concept of a "White Force" will be employed to take advantage of lessons learned from past efforts of this nature and to maximize the technical output from the ICAAS piloted mission simulations. A White Force is an independent, multidisciplinary team that monitors the contractor-conducted simulations to assure technical validity and objectivity in test procedures, data collection and analysis.⁵

Flight Testing

Evaluating the mission contributions of an integrated avionics system through the technique of flight testing is a challenging proposition for an advanced development program. Limitations and obstacles constantly need to be confronted and worked around. Chief among the limitations are the inability to fire real weapons against manned aircraft and restrictions on the use of electronic warfare equipment. The ICAAS program has taken the position that flight testing is necessary, but has limited its scope, cost, and risk by using it primarily as a tool to spot check and validate the manned simulation results.

There are many good reasons for flight testing the ICAAS system. An important but not obvious reason is that flight testing forces the contractor to deliver flightworthy and transitionable computer code rather than deliver the unsubstantiated claim that his code is flightworthy. It is too easy to "fake it" in a simulator environment. As an example, some previously developed attack management code had to be modified extensively to make it acceptable for ICAAS flight testing. First, the flat earth assumption in the code had to be removed. Second, the code would not work with sensor models that accurately reflected the noise and accuracy characteristics of real sensors, and, third, the internetting function worked only with an idealized

high-throughput-rate data link. Bringing the code up to true flightworthy condition was an unexpected task and one that would not have been necessary if the contractor had known from the start that his code would fly in the ICAAS program.

Other justifications for flight testing are more traditional. Flight testing will show effects of the ambient environment on the ICAAS system that can not be addressed in simulation. Sunlight readability of the multi-purpose displays, tactical use of the sun and clouds, effect of background clutter on sensors, and the ability to visually acquire targets when transitioning from Beyond-Visual-Range (BVR) to Within-Visual-Range (WVR) are all factors that are present in flight test but are difficult or impossible to simulate. The ICAAS simulator has a touch sensitive display screen for pilot target designation. It must be shown that this feature is practical under actual flight g loads and buffet conditions. If not, follow-on simulation runs would restrict pilot use of touch sensitive surfaces and revert back to the more conventional cursor control techniques using stick/throttle switches. This could have implications for workload, mission timelines, etc, and could be a factor in the effectiveness of the integrated avionics system. Also, ICAAS includes a control coupler which is a high authority autopilot function. Pilot acceptance of this function may be drastically different in the simulation than in flight because of lack of simulator motion cues. Simulation cannot be used to quantify the g levels, onset rates, roll rates, etc, that a pilot will accept from an automatic system. Flight testing is needed to examine these issues. Finally, the program office believes that demonstration to pilots of the operation of the ICAAS system with actual flight hardware is important. The system must be shown to operate correctly with actual radar noise, inaccuracies of RWR angles, INS drift, data link dropouts, misregistration between the Helmet Mounted Display and HUD, etc, to gain full acceptance from the pilot community.

The ICAAS flight test plan calls for a total of 150 flight hours to be divided between the Air Force Flight Test Center (AFFTC) at Edwards AFB (130 hrs) and the Air Force Tactical Fighter Weapons Center (AFTFWC) at Nellis AFB (20 hrs). The flight test program will start with a single F-15B testbed aircraft equipped with the ICAAS avionics systems and functions (80 flight hours). The cockpit will be modified as shown in Figure 6. A second ICAAS-equipped F-15B will then be added. Both aircraft will be equipped with JTIDS data link terminals. These two internetted aircraft will fly together for 70 hours to demonstrate the cooperative ICAAS operations. As many as four other aircraft at any given time will act as aggressors. Most of the flight test program will take place at AFFTC because of the large amount of system check-out, development, and refinement that is anticipated.

The AFFTC has not traditionally been heavily involved in mission effectiveness flight testing. Providing this environment at the AFFTC within available program resources has led to some

innovative test approaches. An Air Combat Engagement System (ACES) is a computer based emulator of tactical air combat which is embedded in the test aircraft and integrated with applicable on-board avionics systems. Its operation is depicted in Figure 9. ACES provides dynamic combat engagements against as many as eight digitally generated synthetic targets. Targets are interactive, responsive to attacker actions, and capable of realistic maneuvers in attempting to defeat the attack. On-board processing elements are stimulated by the synthetic targets in the same way as with real targets. Missile and gun scoring is available for both sides, as is emulated electronic warfare effects. ACES is expected to greatly reduce the cost of development flight testing at the AFFTC since actual target aircraft are not required and more encounters per flight hour can be performed. An ACES on-ground mode also provides a valuable tool for ground and pre-flight testing.

Figure 9: Air Combat Engagement System (ACES)

Flight testing of the ICAAS missile evasion algorithms presents an interesting challenge. At the AFFTC, real missiles can not be fired and Air Combat Maneuvering Instrumentation (ACMI) scoring capability is not available as it is at the AFFTC. Currently, there are two candidate approaches to working around this limitation. The first approach involves the use of a JTIDS ground station to relay missile shot information to the ICAAS aircraft onboard computers. These JTIDS signals would be initiated by the ground station operator based on radio calls from the aggressor aircraft. The second candidate approach requires the observer pilot in the ICAAS aircraft to listen on the aggressor radio frequency for missile shot calls and to key these events into the ICAAS system through his Multi-Purpose Display. Neither method, of course, involves real missiles or missile warning sensors. A live-fire drone test of the ICAAS missile evasion algorithms in conjunction with an actual missile warning sensor is currently in the planning stages. This testing would be accomplished at Tyndall AFB FL.

Flight testing of the ICAAS integrated avionics system on F-15 aircraft will provide limited real world validation of the mission effectiveness results obtained from manned simulation. Flight testing will also demonstrate to TAC pilots that the system works with real hardware in an actual flight environment. This will instill confidence that the technology is ready for transition for future fighter applications or upgrades to existing fighters.

Concluding Remarks

The systematic build-up approach described for developing and evaluating the ICAAS avionics system is believed to be logical, cost effective, and appropriate to maximize the transition potential of this technology to the operational community. Each evaluation technique has its own strengths, weaknesses, and limitations that must be considered when applying it. The key is to use a combination of techniques that together will give confidence that mission performance levels have been adequately characterized and demonstrated. The ICAAS combination of digital simulation, part task simulation, full-mission simulation, and flight testing is expected to provide this required level of confidence.

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